

The Correlational Study between Happiness and Personality Traits among Graduate Students

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Abstract

Objective of the study: To find out the correlational study between happiness and personality traits among graduate students. Hypotheses: There will be no correlation found between personality traits and happiness among graduate students. Samples:- For the present research, the researcher selected 140 graduate students (70 Boys and 70 Girls) from Nashik City. The age range of subjects 18 to 25 years (M= 20.43, SD = 2.87). Non probability Purposive sampling method was used. Variable:- Personality Traits and 2) Happiness Research Tools. 1. Five Personality Trait Inventory:-2. Happiness Scale. Statistical Analysis: Product moment coefficient correlation (pearson – r) Statistics is used for the present study. Conclusions:- Positive correlation found between personality traits and happiness among graduate students.

Keywords:- Happiness, Personality Traits, Graduate Students, Conscientiousness, Openness, Neuroticism, Agreeableness, Extraversion.

Introduction:

McCrae and Costa (1987) came up with a theory that describes personality as the combination of five main dimensions. This view is commonly referred to as the Big Five factors model. Their goal was to develop a theory that attempted to more specifically describe personality. Extraversion, agreeableness, neuroticism, conscientiousness, and experience-openness are these five characteristics. The degree to which a person is sociable, upbeat, and active is the first dimension, or extraversion. A person who has a high level of extraversion is likely to be talkative, dominant, and gregarious, whereas a person who has a low level of extraversion is likely to be more reserved, unfeeling, and passive. A person's friendliness and compliance are measured by the second factor, agreeableness. A person with a high level of agreeableness will be more jovial, gentle, and trusting, whereas a person with a low level of this variable will be more irritable, cruel, and suspicious.

The third viewpoint, neuroticism, portrays a singular's encounter of gloomy feelings. Those with a high level of neuroticism will be more emotional, prone to vulnerability, and anxious, whereas those with a low level will be calmer, more self-reliant, and experience a greater sense of well-being. Conscientiousness, one of the four factors, describes an individual's level of effort, organization, and self-discipline. Those who have a high level of conscientiousness are driven, ambitious, and responsible, whereas those who have a low

level of this quality are careless, inconsiderate, and irresponsible. Lastly, openness is how much one is creative, imaginative, and interested in intellectual topics. Those with a high openness level are imaginative, creative, and prefer variety, whereas those with a low openness level are mundane, uncreative, and prefer routine.

The Big Five factor model has been empirically validated by extensive research, and additional research demonstrates that measurement of the various factors has high predictive validity on numerous other dimensions, including emotional experience (Cloninger, 2013). Also of interest in this context is research on the relationship between a person's experience of happiness and the Big Five.

The concept of happiness, its definitions, its predictive and determinants, and the connection between happiness and personality have piqued the interest of psychologists over the past decade. Concerning the concept, there are some fundamental questions: Could happiness be regarded as a state produced by a person's circumstances and life event? Does personality have anything to do with it? Or is happiness the result of balancing these two aspects? The prevalent method of studying happiness views it as a trait of the personality -Argyle M, Luo L (1990).

Personality, happiness is a relatively easy concept to define. For example, Bradburn (1969) suggests that happiness is merely experiencing more positive than negative experiences. But what experiences

constitute positive ones and how are they related to happiness? Furthermore, this definition does not explicitly highlight the fact that perhaps an individual's personal disposition could impact whether or not an event is experienced as positive or negative.

Objective of the study:

- 1) To find out the correlational study between happiness and personality traits among graduate students.

Hypotheses:

- 1) There will be no correlation found between personality traits and happiness among graduate students.

Samples:-

For the present research, the researcher selected 140 graduate students (70 Boys and 70 Girls) from Nashik City. The age range of subjects 18 to 25 years (M= 20.43, SD = 2.87). Non probability Purposive sampling method was used.

Variable:-

1) Personality Traits

- i) Conscientiousness
- ii) Openness
- iii) Neuroticism
- iv) Agreeableness
- v) Extraversion

Happiness Research Tools

Five Personality Trait Inventory:-

The present inventory construct and standardized by Prof. K. S. Misra. The author prepared items for measuring each of the five personality traits namely neuroticism, extraversion, openness, agreeableness and

conscientiousness. Five response alternatives were given. They are - 'nearly always, often, many times, rarely and nearly never. A score of 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 were assigned for the five responses namely" 'nearly always, often, many times, rarely and nearly never' respectively. The validity coefficients for conscientiousness, openness, neuroticism, agreeableness and extraversion are .239, .931, .496, .493 and .413.

1) Happiness Scale:-

The response to each item was decided on Likert type Five-point alternative response, viz., Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree and Strongly Disagree and for scoring the responses. The minimum to maximum range of scores as per scoring table 1, was 62 to 310. Reliability - The reliability of the scale was calculated on the basis of split-half (odd-even method). It was calculated to be $r = 0.88$. Validity Items were also validated with an external criteria test Subjective Happiness Scale, which is likert scale as well, the correlation was calculated to be $r = 0.91$.

Statistical Analysis:

Product moment coefficient correlation (pearson – r) Statistics is used for the present study.

Statistical Interpretation and Discussion

Showing the Correlation between personality traits and happiness among graduate students.

Table No-1

Traits	Conscientiousness	Openness	Neuroticism	Agreeableness	Extraversion	Happiness
Conscientiousness	0	.56	-.42	.75	.63	.81
Openness	.56	0	-.33	.71	.82	.88
Neuroticism	-.42	-.33	0	-.23	-.52	-.12
Agreeableness	.75	.71	-.23	0	.68	.78
Extraversion	.63	.82	-.52	.68	0	.79
Happiness	.81	.88	-.12	.78	.79	0

Significant level 0.05=0.09 0.01=0.13 NS=Not Significant

The result showed that there is significant positive correlation between Conscientiousness and Openness ($r=.56$), Conscientiousness and Agreeableness ($r=.75$), Conscientiousness and Extraversion ($r=.63$), Conscientiousness and Happiness ($r=.81$). Negative correlation between Conscientiousness and Neuroticism ($r= -.42$).

In the result table 1 we can see that correlation found between personality traits and happiness among graduate students. Here correlation is significant at 0.01 level.

While some studies of social behaviour, e.g. Argyle, Martin and Cross land (1989) have acknowledged the role of personality variables like extraversion, its relationship to happiness appears to be mediated through assertiveness in extraverts' social behaviour, Lu (1990b), rather than any inherent bias towards happiness for extraverts, as suggested by Gray (1972) though such a bias could affect their confidence and assertiveness. So, since there is evidence for both effects, social behaviour could contribute, in conjunction with E, to a person's characteristic degree of happiness

Conclusions:-

- 1) Positive correlation found between personality traits and happiness among graduate students.

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